

Original Research

Service Quality and its Impact on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty: Evidence from Pharmaceutical Importers in Liberia

Diana M. Garkpeh ¹, Lawrence G. Saye ^{1*}

¹Business School of Hohai University, Hohai University, Nanjing 211100, China

Article history:

Received: 15 April 2025

Accepted: 21 April 2025

Published Online: 30 April 2025

*Correspondence:

Business School of Hohai University,
Hohai University, Nanjing 211100,
China

How to cite this article:

Author, Diana M. Garkpeh,
Lawrence G. Saye (2025). Service
Quality and its Impact on Customer
Satisfaction and Loyalty: Evidence
from Pharmaceutical Importers in
Liberia. North American Academic
Research, 8(4), 286-301. doi:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1531338>

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations. **Copyright:** ©2025 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Abstract

The pharmaceutical sector is one of the most important sectors in Liberia in that it is linked to the health sector. Pharmaceutical importers import health products into the country to help sick patients however, the sector is faced with some challenges. Even though this sector is of great importance to the country enough studies have not concentrated on them. This gap was sought to be filled with this current study. The main aim of this study examine the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction and loyalty in the pharmaceutical industry. Customer satisfaction has been focused on by most commercial organizations and sectors with little emphasis on the health sectors. Customer satisfaction is seen to have a ripple effect on consumer loyalty. This study used the SERVQUAL model to assess this relationship because it provides the researcher with the flexibility to use the dimensions of service quality. This study employed a descriptive quantitative method with the use of Likert scale questionnaires to gather data. The diversity of the participants in terms of the diverse socio-demographic characteristics helped the data to be heterogeneous. The Cronbach alpha coefficient was used to assess the internal consistency of the items used which also showed the reliability of the instruments. To assess the hypothesis of this study between the above mentioned variables, the regression analysis was conducted. The result of the analysis indicated that, there is a strong positive relationship between service quality and overall customer satisfaction. Also, the study further proved that service quality positively influences consumer loyalty. Thus, the study further proves the assertion of the SERVQUAL model which claims that the dimensions of service quality positively affect the customer's satisfaction and consumer loyalty. Based on these conclusions the study recommended ways in which the pharmaceutical industry can improve on their service quality. Paying attention to customers, meeting their needs timely, and being reliable are the few ways to ensure attaining high levels of service quality.

Keywords: Service Quality; Customer Satisfaction; Customer Loyalty; SERVQUAL; Regression

1 Introduction

Characteristics of the service, which are intangible, heterogeneous, inseparable, and perishable, make it challenging for retailers to measure an organization's service quality [1]. Some services are perceived as intangible, and others are

perceived as tangible. For example, one can find it very hard to understand the feelings that consumers possess towards a particular product. Regardless of the complexity associated with estimating these intangible attributes, measuring service quality is essential because consumers expect retailers and manufacturers to satisfy their expectations [2]. Previous works have demonstrated the existing relationship between service quality (SQ), customer satisfaction (CS), customer loyalty (CL), and Repurchase intention (RI) to a greater extent [1, 3-6]. For any business or industry to stay relevant, it must seek to satisfy customers such that they will repurchase its products. The key to surviving in a global market is to focus on customer service quality [7]. This statement helps to predetermine the relationship that exists between service quality, consumer loyalty, and customer satisfaction, and this is the focus of the current study. To support this claim with literature, the next paragraph will present a few studies that have explored these relationships in detail.

During these few decades, various studies have stated that there is a relationship between customer satisfaction and services provided by an organization [8-11]. Customer satisfaction is seen as one of the major factors that influences customer loyalty to organizations [12]. It is also worth noting that customer loyalty is seen to have an indirect relationship with organizational performance because of the extended relationship that exists between customer loyalty and customers' intention to repurchase [13]. This relationship has made it so that the issue of customer satisfaction is prominent in many organizations. Organizations can claim success when customer satisfaction is attained [7]. Based on this background, this study can postulate a triad relationship between SQ, CS, and CL, which will be discussed in detail in the conceptual framework section. To zoom in on the details of these factors, the question remains what it is about service quality that has much influence on these two variables, such that it can be seen as the independent variable, and the others (CS and CL) can be seen as dependent variables? From the broad perspective of concepts, service quality can entail the degree to which an organization provides the best services to its consumers. This can infer that the quality of service can be judged by the recipient and not the producer and this is why customers' opinions are needed in such value judgments.

There are interesting statistics on what normally happens when a customer is satisfied. These recent data demonstrate four things which usually happen when a customer is satisfied and these include; first and foremost a satisfied customer is likely to communicate their satisfaction to 9-10 people, while a dissatisfied customer reports his dissatisfaction to 15-20 people; secondly, for every 1% increase in customer satisfaction, there is an average increase of 2.4% return on investment; also, the cost of recruiting a new customer is 5-10 times greater than the cost of keeping a satisfied customer; and finally, if the Quality of Service perception is particularly poor, 91% of retail customers will not return [14]. Based on these details, an organization can't afford to meet the quality of its customers because the detrimental effect will be on the organization's performance. A social concept like service quality will suffice in every industry and as such this study decided to study one of the industries that faces various pressures from its customers in Liberia, the pharmaceutical industry.

As any other industry, the pharmaceutical industry faces a lot of service quality issues especially since its products are seen as very important. From an observational point of view, this industry is linked with the health sector and the majority of the populace uses their services one or the other. If not 100% of adults, it can be argued that every individual who has engaged with the hospitals has engaged with pharmaceutical products. As a result, this is an industry that produces services for the masses. This makes conducting a study in this field essential for the industry as well as the country as a whole. Liberia, a small country on the west coast of Africa, has a relatively small but rapidly growing pharmaceutical market [15]. The country's healthcare system is still recovering from the effects of the civil war that ended in 2003, which left the country's infrastructure and essential services in tatters [16]. As a result, there is a great need for pharmaceutical products, making the country an attractive market for pharmaceutical importers. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), Liberia had an estimated population of 4.8 million in 2020, with a projected 3.6% population growth rate [17]. This growing population, coupled with an increase in chronic diseases like HIV/AIDS, malaria, and tuberculosis, has resulted in a high demand for pharmaceutical products. The Liberian pharmaceutical market is primarily import-based, with a limited number of local pharmaceutical manufacturers.

In light of these challenges, there has been a growing interest in studying the effects of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty in the pharmaceutical industry. Several studies have been conducted in recent years to explore the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty in the pharmaceutical industry [18-20]. They investigated the importance of service quality in the pharmaceutical industry and found that customers were more likely to be satisfied and loyal to an importer if they perceived high levels of service quality. This study provided an initial understanding of the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction and loyalty in the pharmaceutical industry.

2 Literature review and model framework

2.1 Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty

Customer satisfaction can be seen as a fundamental aspect of business operations, emphasizing its role in shaping a company's future prospects [21]. Several key factors contribute to customer satisfaction, including product and service quality, emotional response, and pricing [22]. When businesses consistently meet customer expectations, they enhance customer loyalty, which, in turn, improves financial performance and long-term sustainability. Customer loyalty is closely linked to satisfaction, as businesses that successfully retain their customers benefit from increased profitability and brand advocacy. Customer loyalty has been seen to be crucial for improving financial performance and sustaining a company [22]. However, achieving customer loyalty is a multi-stage process involving attracting and converting new customers, ensuring repeat purchases, and developing brand advocates [23]. Customer loyalty traits include: regular purchases, resistance to competitors, and strong brand commitment. It is worth noting that retaining existing customers is more cost-effective than acquiring new ones, as loyal customers not only provide a steady revenue stream but also reduce marketing costs through word-of-mouth promotion [23].

Numerous studies have examined the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty across different industries. In the banking sector, e-banking in Hong Kong revealed that security and efficiency significantly impacted customer satisfaction and future consumer behavior [24]. Similarly, in Pakistan, the banking sector found that tangibles, reliability, assurance, and empathy are key service quality dimensions influencing satisfaction and loyalty. In the telecommunication sector, several studies have confirmed the positive relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction [25-27]. Despite the extensive research on service quality and customer satisfaction across various industries, very few studies have focused on Liberia's pharmaceutical import sector. Given the critical role of pharmaceutical imports in national healthcare [28], this study aims to address this gap by examining the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty in Liberia's pharmaceutical industry. Based on the established relationship in literature, we hypothesise that;

Hypothesis 1: Customer satisfaction has a direct influence on customer loyalty among pharmaceutical importers in Liberia.

2.2 Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty

Tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy which are the key components of service quality have been seen to significantly influence customer loyalty in the pharmaceutical and healthcare services [29]. Ismail and Yunan (2016) [30] found that service quality dimensions' shape customer perceptions and loyalty. Other studies also found that customer satisfaction mediates between service quality and loyalty, stressing the importance of meeting customers' expectations. A similar study like ours in the health sector, Yousapronpaiboon (2014) [31] evaluates service quality in public hospital pharmacies using the SERVQUAL model, finding assurance and empathy to be strong areas, while responsiveness and tangibles require improvement. These findings suggest a need for further research into how service quality factors influence customer satisfaction in different pharmaceutical settings.

In south African retail pharmacies, gaps between customer expectations and perceived service quality were identified [32]. The study highlights the need for improvements in tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy to enhance customer satisfaction and market competitiveness. Afolabi and Osemene (2020) [33] conducted a cross-sectional survey in Sierra Leone to evaluate consumer satisfaction with healthcare services in community pharmacies. Their study, involving 583 participants, finds that the most sought-after services include patient counseling, medication purchases, and minor ailment treatments, while screening services and sexuality education remain limited. Similarly, Ihekoronye et al. (2021) [34] examine customer perspectives on pharmacy service quality in Nigeria, identifying significant gaps between customer expectations and the responsiveness and reliability of pharmacy teams. Their findings underscore the need for pharmacies to improve service delivery and customer engagement.

Jande et al. (2013) [35] assessed patient satisfaction in Tanzanian hospital pharmacies by surveying 401 outpatients. Their study emphasizes the role of polite pharmacists and reputable medical practitioners in attracting patients but identifies long wait times and medication unavailability as key areas for improvement. The existing literature demonstrates that service quality has a profound impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty in the pharmaceutical industry. Thus, two hypotheses were deduced from this discussion;

Hypothesis 2: There is a positive relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction among pharmaceutical importers in Liberia.

Hypothesis 3: Service quality has an indirect effect on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction among pharmaceutical importers in Liberia

2.3 The SERVQUAL Model

Parasuraman et al. (1985) [36] identified 97 attributes that influence service quality, which were categorized into ten dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, communication, credibility, security, competence, courtesy, understanding customers, and access. These attributes were later refined through a two-stage purification process to enhance the reliability and validity of the assessment instrument (Parasuraman et al., 1988) [37]. The first stage retained

the ten dimensions, while the second stage focused on scale dimensionality and reliability, ultimately reducing them to five key dimensions:

Tangibility – Physical facilities, equipment, and appearance of personnel.

Reliability – The ability to perform the promised service accurately and dependably.

Responsiveness – Willingness to help customers and provide prompt service.

Assurance – Knowledge and courtesy of employees, instilling trust and confidence.

Empathy – Personalized attention and care provided to customers.

The SERVQUAL model, developed through this process, consists of 22 statements derived from the original 97 attributes, tested across five independent service industries to ensure reliability and validity. The findings demonstrated low correlation among the five dimensions, confirming their independence as distinct factors in assessing service quality (Parasuraman et al., 1988) [37]. Further empirical tests verified the model's content validity by assessing how thoroughly the scale represented the service quality construct. Convergent validity was established by analyzing the relationship between SERVQUAL scores and customer ratings of overall service quality (Parasuraman et al., 1988) [37]. Initially designed for service and retail businesses, the SERVQUAL model enables organizations to assess customer perceptions, track service quality over time, and identify performance gaps that require strategic improvements. Parasuraman et al. (1988) [37] recommend using SERVQUAL three to four times annually to monitor service quality fluctuations and evaluate discrepancies between expected and perceived service. Additionally, they suggest integrating SERVQUAL with other models, such as employee perception assessments, to gain a holistic understanding of service quality. The model can also be adapted as a weighted SERVQUAL model, prioritizing dimensions based on their relative importance to customers. By segmenting customers based on their SERVQUAL scores, businesses can tailor service improvements to meet varying customer expectations, enhancing overall satisfaction and profitability. Overall, SERVQUAL remains a widely used tool for measuring service quality, helping businesses maintain high standards and improve customer experiences. Its ability to pinpoint service gaps makes it an essential framework for achieving long-term business success and customer loyalty.

2.3.1 The functioning of the SERVQUAL model

SERVQUAL represents service quality as the discrepancy between a customer's expectations for a service offering and the customer's perceptions of the service received, requiring respondents to answer questions about both their expectations and their perceptions Parasuraman et al., (1988) [37]. The use of perceived as opposed to actual service received makes the SERVQUAL measure an attitude measure that is related to, but not the same as, satisfaction (Parasuraman et. al., 1988) [37]. The difference between expectations and perceptions is called the gap which is the determinant of customers' perception of service quality as shown on Figure 1 below.

Figure. 1: Measuring service quality using SERVQUAL model

Source: Kumar et al. (2009)

This model explains the underlying process, which is applied to guide this study. The SERVQUAL model is suitable for measuring service quality and customer satisfaction using the service quality dimensions. The SERVQUAL approach

integrates the two constructs and suggests that perceived service quality is an antecedent to satisfaction. Therefore, in this research, the initial 22 items of the SERVQUAL model are modified and additional items are included to measure the perceived service quality and customer satisfaction in the use of pharmaceutical products. The model is a summary for the 24 items and we want to find out the overall service quality perceived by customers and which dimensions customers are satisfied with.

3 Research methods

3.1 Research design

This study employed a cross-sectional quantitative research design, which is appropriate for examining the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty at a specific point in time. A cross-sectional design allows for the collection of data from a large sample at a single moment, enabling researchers to identify patterns, correlations, and trends without requiring a longitudinal commitment [38]. Given the study's objective, to assess the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty among pharmaceutical importers in Liberia, this approach ensures efficient data collection and facilitates statistical analysis to derive meaningful insights. The quantitative aspect of the study ensures that findings are objective, measurable, and generalizable. By utilizing structured surveys or questionnaires, numerical data can be collected and analyzed using statistical methods, providing a clear understanding of the relationships between key variables [39]. This method enhances the reliability and validity of the study while minimizing researcher bias. Furthermore, a cross-sectional approach is particularly beneficial in business and service research, as it enables decision-makers to understand customer perceptions at a given time and make informed strategic choices based on empirical evidence. The study's use of this design ensures a systematic and structured investigation of how service quality influences customer satisfaction and loyalty in Liberia's pharmaceutical import sector.

3.2 Study Area

At the time this research was conducted, there were 52 licensed pharmaceutical businesses operating in Liberia, according to data obtained from the Liberia Medicines and Health Products Regulatory Authority (LMHRA) – Inspectorate Department (Premise). These licensed pharmaceutical businesses play a crucial role in ensuring the availability of essential medicines and healthcare products across the country. The LMHRA is the official regulatory body responsible for overseeing the pharmaceutical sector, ensuring compliance with national and international standards, and maintaining the safety, efficacy, and quality of pharmaceutical products available to the public. The study specifically focused on pharmaceutical businesses operating in urban and semi-urban areas, where access to pharmaceutical services is more concentrated. The key locations included Monrovia, Paynesville, Buchanan, Gbarnga, and Kakata, which serve as major commercial and healthcare hubs in Liberia. These cities were chosen because they host a significant number of licensed pharmaceutical companies, wholesalers, retailers, and healthcare providers, making them ideal locations for assessing customer satisfaction and loyalty within the pharmaceutical sector. Monrovia, the capital and largest city, is home to the majority of Liberia's pharmaceutical importers, wholesalers, and retail pharmacies. Paynesville, a rapidly growing urban area, also has a high concentration of pharmacies serving a dense population. Buchanan, an important port city, facilitates the importation and distribution of pharmaceutical products. Gbarnga, as the central regional hub, ensures pharmaceutical access to rural areas, while Kakata serves as a key commercial center with an expanding pharmaceutical market. Given Liberia's growing demand for high-quality pharmaceutical services, assessing customer satisfaction and loyalty in this industry is essential for improving service quality. By analyzing pharmaceutical businesses licensed by the LMHRA, this study provides valuable insights that can help enhance service delivery, strengthen regulatory compliance, and promote greater customer trust and loyalty within Liberia's healthcare sector.

3.3 Population of the study

The population of this study comprises customers and stakeholders associated with the 52 licensed pharmaceutical businesses operating in Liberia, as documented by the Liberia Medicines and Health Products Regulatory Authority (LMHRA) – Inspectorate Department (Premise). These businesses, located in urban and semi-urban areas such as Monrovia, Paynesville, Buchanan, Gbarnga, and Kakata, play a critical role in ensuring the availability of essential medicines and healthcare products across the country. The study specifically targeted customers who have utilized pharmaceutical services within the past six months, as well as stakeholders including distributors, retailers, and healthcare professionals (e.g., pharmacists, doctors, and nurses) who interact directly with these businesses.

The selected cities serve as major commercial and healthcare hubs, with Monrovia hosting the majority of pharmaceutical importers, wholesalers, and retail pharmacies, while Paynesville, Buchanan, Gbarnga, and Kakata represent key distribution and access points for both urban and rural populations. By focusing on these areas, the study captures a diverse and representative sample of respondents, ensuring that the findings reflect the dynamics of customer satisfaction and loyalty within Liberia's pharmaceutical sector. This population aligns with the study's objectives and provides a robust foundation for analyzing the impact of service quality on customer perceptions and experiences.

3.4 Sample Design

The quantitative nature of the study ensured a representative sample, thus, the study employed a non-probability sampling technique, specifically convenience sampling. This method was chosen due to the accessibility of respondents and the feasibility of data collection within the pharmaceutical sector in Liberia. Convenience sampling allows researchers to target individuals who are readily available and willing to participate, making it an efficient approach given time and resource constraints. The sample included customers of pharmaceutical companies, pharmacists, distributors, and healthcare professionals who regularly interact with pharmaceutical services. This selection ensures that the study captures a diverse range of perspectives on service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty. The respondents were chosen based on their experience with pharmaceutical services, ensuring that they could provide meaningful insights relevant to the research objectives. To determine an appropriate sample size, the study considered previous research in similar fields and used Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) sample size determination table as a reference. Given the study's focus on quantitative analysis, a larger sample size was preferred to enhance the statistical validity and reliability of the findings, thus 202 respondents were selected for the study.

3.5 Data Collection

Primary data were collected for this study, as they are tailored to the specific objectives of the research and provide authentic and accurate insights. For this research, a self-administered questionnaire was used as the primary data collection instrument. The questionnaire was designed based on the SERVQUAL model and utilized a 7-point Likert scale to measure respondents' perceptions. It was divided into three sections: Section A: Collected demographic information about the respondents, such as age, gender, occupation, and frequency of interaction with pharmaceutical services. Section B: Focused on the five dimensions of service quality (tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy) as outlined in the SERVQUAL model. Section C: Assessed customer satisfaction and loyalty through statements rated by respondents based on their level of agreement.

The questionnaire was developed after a thorough review of theoretical literature and previous studies, ensuring its relevance to the research objectives and context. Data collection took place over a period of six months, targeting customers and stakeholders of the 52 licensed pharmaceutical businesses operating in urban and semi-urban areas of Liberia, including Monrovia, Paynesville, Buchanan, Gbarnga, and Kakata. A total of 202 respondents were targeted, comprising customers, distributors, retailers, and healthcare professionals. The questionnaires were distributed conveniently via email and social media platforms, with follow-up reminders sent through phone calls to ensure a high response rate. Respondents were selected based on their regular interaction with pharmaceutical services and their ability to provide informed feedback on service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty. This approach ensured that the data collected were both representative and reliable, aligning with the study's descriptive research design and providing a robust foundation for analysis.

4.7 Data Analysis Techniques

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software (SPSS 29 version). First, a descriptive analysis summarized the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Next, inferential statistics were used using regression analysis to examine the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty. Data analysis was done by using the statistical software SPSS (29.0 version). Descriptive statistics, such as mean, standard deviation, and frequency distribution, were used to summarize the data. Multiple Regression analysis was performed to identify the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty. The regression model for testing the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty to pharmaceutical importers in Liberia is originally structured as follows:

$$Y_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 + \beta_2 + \beta_3 + \beta_4 + \beta_5 + \varepsilon \text{ -----(2)}$$

$$Y_2 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 + \beta_2 + \beta_3 + \beta_4 + \beta_5 + \varepsilon \text{ ----- (3)}$$

Where:

Y1= Customer Satisfaction (CS)

Y2= Customer Loyalty

β_0 = The Constant

β_1 -5= represents the coefficients that measure the impact of service quality on customer namely; Tangibility, Reliability, Assurance, Empathy, and Responsiveness

ε =error term and since this is a social science study we will assume a 0.05% error margin

3 Results and discussion

In Figure 2, the gender distribution among the 202 respondents is approximately equal, with 54.0% male (109 respondents) and 46.0% female (93 respondents). The equal presence of male and female participants in the research

study guarantees that diverse perspectives are incorporated, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of customer satisfaction and loyalty dynamics in the pharmaceutical importing sector. This is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure. 4.2: Gender distribution of the respondents

Based on age, most respondents are in the younger age range. 33.7% (68 respondents) fall within the 20-30 age group, while 32.7% (66 respondents) are within the 31-40 age group. In addition, 28.2% (57 participants) fall within the age range of 41-50 years, 5.0% (10 participants) fall within the age range of 51-60 years, and only 0.5% (1 participant) is 60 years or older. The age distribution in the study suggests that the investigation predominantly represents the views of younger professionals. This is important for the study since younger participants may have distinct expectations and experiences about service quality, which could affect the overall results. This outcome is also illustrated in Figure 3. Additionally, most respondents (48.0%, or 97 individuals) work in the Sales and Marketing field, while 19.8% (40) are Customer Service Representatives. Operations & Logistics represent 12.9% (26 respondents), Directors constitute 9.9% (20 respondents), and the remaining 9.4% (19 respondents) belong to the 'Others' category as illustrated in Figure 4. The data on occupational distribution indicates that most respondents deal with customers directly.

Figure. 4.2: Gender distribution of the respondents

Due to their direct engagement with customers, they are in a favorable position to offer valuable insights into the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction and loyalty. The majority of responders have a high level of educational attainment. More precisely, 59.9% of the respondents own an undergraduate degree, which amounts to 121 individuals.

Figure. 4.3: The work position of the respondents

Additionally, 20.8% of the respondents, equivalent to 42 individuals, hold a Master's degree. Furthermore, 2.0% of the respondents, four individuals, have obtained a PhD. In addition, 17.3% of the respondents, corresponding to 35 individuals, possess a high school graduation. The respondents' high educational attainment implies that they possess extensive knowledge and can offer insightful and analytical perspectives on service quality matters. The substantial proportion of participants possessing postgraduate degrees further suggests that the results are derived from the viewpoints of well-educated experts in the field. Finally, the educational level of the participants is shown in Figure 5.

Figure. 4.3: The educational level of respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Female	93	46.0	46.0	46.0
Male	109	54.0	54.0	100.0
Age				
20-30 years	68	33.7	33.7	33.7
31-40 years	66	32.7	32.7	66.3
41-50 years	57	28.2	28.2	94.6
51-60 years	10	5.0	5.0	99.5
61 or >	1	.5	.5	100.0
Work Position				
Customer Service Representative	40	19.8	19.8	19.8
Representative	20	9.9	9.9	29.7

Director	1	.5	.5	30.2
Operations	26	12.9	12.9	43.1
Others	18	8.9	8.9	52.0
Sales and Marketing	97	48.0	48.0	100.0
Experience				
11-15 years	32	15.8	15.8	15.8
15 years and more	7	3.5	3.5	19.3
5-10 years	111	55.0	55.0	74.3
Below 5 years	52	25.7	25.7	100.0
Educational Status				
High School Diploma	35	17.3	17.3	17.3
Master	42	20.8	20.8	38.1
PHD	4	2.0	2.0	40.1
Undergraduate	121	59.9	59.9	100.0
Distribution Channel				
Healthcare	59	29.2	29.2	29.2
Retailers	101	50.0	50.0	79.2
Wholesalers	42	20.8	20.8	100.0
Income per month				
25,000LRD or below	23	11.4	11.4	11.4
26,000-35,000 LRD	46	22.8	22.8	34.2
36,000-45,000 LRD	53	26.2	26.2	60.4
46,000-55,000 LRD	40	19.8	19.8	80.2
56,000 LRD and >	40	19.8	19.8	100.0

Table 4:1 Summary of socio-demographic of respondents

4.2 Statistical Analysis

The first analysis conducted was to ascertain the description of the table. This helps us to understand the distribution of the items distributed to the respondent. The Likert scale was used to assess the apprehension of the respondents and these items were finally grouped under the main subheadings of the dimensions of service quality. These items are grouped under tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, awareness, and empathy.

4.2 Statistical Analysis

The first analysis conducted was to ascertain the description of the table. This helps us to understand the distribution of the items distributed to the respondent. The Likert scale was used to assess the apprehension of the respondents and these items were finally grouped under the main subheadings of the dimensions of service quality. These items are grouped under tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, awareness, and empathy.

4.2.1 Descriptive Statistics

		Min	Max	Mean	Std.	Std. Dev	Skewness	Kurtosis		
	N			Statistic	Error	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Error	Error
Tangibility	202	1.50	7.00	4.3783	.11260	1.60028	.167	.171	-1.277	.341
Reliability	202	1.40	7.00	4.3911	.10770	1.53075	.040	.171	-1.233	.341
Responsiveness	202	1.00	7.00	4.5965	.10127	1.43926	.092	.171	-1.097	.341
Awareness	202	1.75	7.00	4.8020	.10343	1.46998	-.171	.171	-1.096	.341
Empathy	202	1.80	7.00	4.7861	.10343	1.47003	-.158	.171	-1.147	.341

Table 4:2 Descriptive of Service Quality Measurement

The descriptive statistics provide important information on the relationships between the dimensions of service quality and customer satisfaction and loyalty not only concerning the pharmaceutical importers in Liberia but also in general. All variables were assessed using a 7-point Likert-type scale in which 1 referred to strongly disagree and 7 strongly agreed. Analysis of each of these variables helps in the understanding of the concept of service quality from the perspective of the customers, the resultant satisfaction, and loyalty. This description of the items used for the study gives us a preamble for the analysis of the other sections. The results from the descriptive analysis indicates that the responses from the customers of the pharmaceutical services were high. This gives us an idea of how effective these variables are for study.

4.2.2 Reliability test

One of the main advantages of the use of the quantitative method is that it provides reliable findings that can be used by

other researchers in similar studies. This tests the consistency of the used items and the grounds to trust its findings. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient is best known to help assess the internal consistency of the data. The results of the reliability test are depicted in Table 4.3. The replicability of the study based on the use of the same or similar instruments cannot be overstated as the aim of the research endeavor. Thus, the internal consistency of the SERVQUAL items was assessed by computing the total reliability scale which gave the study the base to place it in a better quantitative stance. The total reliability scale for the study is 0.92, indicating an overall reliability factor similar to that of the study on the same variables used which was 0.92[40]. This reliability value for this study is substantial because the highest reliability that can be obtained is 1.0 and this is an indication that the items of the five dimensions of the SERVQUAL model are accepted for analysis. Table 4.3 above shows the reliability scale for all 5 dimensions and also, the reliability scale for each dimension calculated when each item is deleted from the dimension to see if the deleted item is genuine or not. In case Cronbach's alpha for a dimension increases when an item is deleted it shows that the item is not genuine in that dimension. Therefore, overall these are the implications that can be made from this study. The reliability analysis of the study dimensions indicates that all constructs demonstrate good internal consistency, as evidenced by their Cronbach's alpha values exceeding 0.8. Cronbach's alpha measures how well a set of items function together to assess a specific concept, with values above 0.7 generally considered acceptable. In this study, all dimensions—Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Awareness, and Empathy—exhibit strong reliability, suggesting that the items within each category effectively measure their respective constructs. The reliability analysis demonstrates that all study dimensions exhibit strong internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha values well above the acceptable threshold. No items should be removed, as each contributes positively to its respective dimension. These findings validate the reliability of the measurement instrument and support its use in assessing service quality effectively.

Dimension	Number of Items	Cronbach alpha for dimensions	Cronbach alpha if item deleted	Item
Tangibles	4	0.885	0.850	TA1
			0.840	TA2
			0.848	TA3
			0.868	TA4
Reliability	5	0.889	0.869	RL1
			0.855	RL2
			0.871	RL3
			0.863	RL4
			0.865	RL5
Responsiveness	4	0.835	0.787	RN1
			0.782	RN2
			0.789	RN3
			0.810	RN4
Awareness	4	0.872	0.851	AS1
			0.819	AS2
			0.825	AS3
			0.850	AS4
Empathy	5	0.883	0.875	EM1
			0.849	EM2
			0.855	EM3
			0.846	EM4
			0.863	EM5

Table 4:3 Reliability coefficient (Cronbach's alpha)

4.2.3 Factor analysis for the dimensions of service quality

	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
TA1	.714					
TA2	.614					
TA3	.609					
TA4	.713					
RL1		.623				
RL2		.740				
RL3		.619				

RL4	.652			
RL5	.630			
RN1		.570		
RN2		.630		
RN3		.604		.744
RN4		.713		
AS1				
AS2			.691	
AS3			.600	
AS4			.604	
EM1			.740	
EM2				
EM3				
EM4		.811		
EM5		.773		

Table 4:5 Rotated component matrix

Table 4.5 shows the factor loadings for each item about the various factors. The rotated component matrix from your Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with Varimax rotation reveals several important insights into the factor structure of the data. The purpose of PCA in this context is to identify underlying factors that explain the relationships between the observed variables, and the Varimax rotation method ensures that each variable loads strongly on one factor while minimizing cross-loadings. This approach helps clarify how the various items (or variables) in the study are grouped together based on their correlations, making it easier to interpret the dimensions that they represent.

The factor structure uncovered by the PCA reveals that the dimensions of service quality in this study—Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Awareness, and Empathy—are interrelated but distinct. There is clear evidence that Responsiveness and Empathy are closely tied together, highlighting the importance of emotional and relational aspects in service interactions. Tangibles and Reliability, while related, appear to operate somewhat independently of the other dimensions. Awareness is also a separate factor, suggesting that the understanding of customer needs plays a distinct but equally important role in the service experience. These findings provide a robust framework for understanding how different aspects of service quality are structured and interrelated in your study. The results offer valuable insights into how customers perceive service quality, and the relationships between the various dimensions can inform both the theoretical understanding and practical application of your findings.

4.3 Regression Analysis

The regression analysis helped us to test the hypothesis stated above. This regression analysis aimed to help ascertain the degree to which one variable influences the other and the extent of this effect. The first regression helped to assess the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction. Also, it is worth noting that because the study employed Likert scales in data collection, the ordinal analysis was conducted.

4.3.1 Regression model 1: Service quality and customer satisfaction

The Model Summary and Coefficients tables provide insights into the regression analysis conducted to predict overall satisfaction based on the five predictor variables: Empathy, Reliability, Tangibility, Awareness, and Responsiveness. The Model Summary table provides an overview of the fit of the regression model. The R-value of 0.726 indicates a strong positive relationship between the predictors (Empathy, Reliability, Tangibility, Awareness, and Responsiveness) and overall satisfaction. An R Square value of 0.527 means that 52.7% of the variance in overall satisfaction is explained by these five predictors. This suggests that while the model accounts for a good portion of the variance, other factors outside the model could also be influencing satisfaction.

Model Summary									
		Change Statistics							
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change
1	.726 ^a	.527	.515	1.2056	.527	43.725	5	196	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy, Reliability, Tangibility, Awareness, Responsiveness

Table 4:7 Service quality and customer satisfaction

4.3.2 Regression Model 2: Service quality and Consumer loyalty

This model seeks to answer the how service quality impacts consumer loyalty with emphasis on the for components of service quality. The Model Summary provides an overview of the relationship between the predictor variables (Empathy, Reliability, Tangibility, Awareness, and Responsiveness) and the dependent variable, consumer loyalty. The R-value of

0.732 indicates a moderately strong positive correlation between the predictors and consumer loyalty, meaning that these variables together are fairly effective at explaining variations in consumer loyalty. The R Square value of 0.536 means that 53.6% of the variation in consumer loyalty can be accounted for by the five predictors in the model. This suggests that these variables collectively have a decent amount of explanatory power, although there is still a significant portion of variability in consumer loyalty that is not captured by the model. The regression model explains a substantial portion of the variation in consumer loyalty (53.6%), with Responsiveness emerging as the most significant predictor. This suggests that customers value how quickly and effectively their service needs are addressed. Awareness is also a significant predictor, emphasizing the importance of understanding and meeting customer needs. While Empathy shows some influence, it is not as strong, and Tangibility and Reliability do not significantly predict consumer loyalty in this model. The lack of significance for Tangibility and Reliability suggests that factors related to emotional connection (Responsiveness and Awareness) may be more important drivers of loyalty than the functional aspects of service delivery in this context. The model's findings suggest that service providers aiming to improve consumer loyalty should prioritize responsiveness and awareness, while also paying attention to the emotional and relational aspects of customer interactions.

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Change Statistics				Sig. Change	F
				RStd. Error of the Estimate	Change	F Change	df1		
1	.732 ^a	.536	.525	1.1811	.536	45.369	5	196	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy, Reliability, Tangibility, Awareness, Responsiveness

Table 4:8 Service quality and Consumer loyalty

4.4 Discussion

The pharmaceutical industry, particularly the importers in Liberia, plays a vital role in guaranteeing the presence and reachability of necessary medications and medical supplies. Due to the crucial nature of their services, the quality offered by pharmaceutical importers plays a vital role in determining customer satisfaction and loyalty. The performed empirical study emphasizes the influential roles of different characteristics of service quality, such as tangibility, reliability, assurance, empathy, and responsiveness this confirms evidence from prior literature though from different sectors but same results [41,42]. Consumer satisfaction is a crucial factor that indicates the extent to which a service meets or beyond consumer expectations, and it is a key determinant of client loyalty. The regression analysis results demonstrate that tangibility, which refers to the physical elements of service delivery, such as the appearance of buildings, equipment, and personnel, strongly impacts customer satisfaction. This finding affirm the general assertion that the higher the perceived service quality the higher the satisfaction of the consumer [43]. The government must encourage modernizing facilities and ensure that the people working for the pharmaceutical importers are neatly dressed. These physical aspects positively influence the customers' perception of the quality of service.

Another factor that adds to customer satisfaction is reliability, which is the ability of the firm to deliver the services in the required and agreed manner. In the pharma sector, the delivery of products is the most crucial issue and clients expect the products to be delivered to them accurately and on time. Achieving these expectations means the satisfaction level goes up, thus the importance of operation effectiveness and accuracy. Pharmaceutical product importers must ensure they can meet their commitments to improve client satisfaction and increase customer loyalty. The element of assurance, which encompasses personnel's knowledge and courtesy and their ability to create confidence in customers, has a strong and positive influence on satisfaction levels. There is a positive relationship between customer satisfaction and their perception of competency as well as courtesy of the staff. The finding underlines the need to invest funds in training and development activities for the employees to ensure they have adequate capacity and knowledge to offer high-quality services. Employees who can create confidence enhance the level of satisfaction of the clients since the clients are assured of the quality of the service being delivered as well as its reliability.

The last of the marketing concepts is called Empathy, which is the process of offering consumer-oriented and humane care to consumers and is essential to enhancing the level of customer satisfaction. Perceiving the needs of the other party has a large role in the pharmaceutical business since clients often need personalized consultation and support. Customers also love to be attended to individually and with much attention, as this makes them feel special. Pharmaceutical importers should consider improving the level of customer service and the kind of interaction between them and their customers to be able to build a closer relationship with their clients, which will automatically lead to satisfaction. The tendency to help the consumers and provide service when needed, known as Responsiveness, is positively related to customer satisfaction. However, it is not as important as Assurance and Empathy. Nevertheless, customers still care about the time, and the immediate response to requests and problems can positively affect the customer's perception of the service. Pharmaceutical importers need to pay significant attention to response because it relates to the quality-of-service delivery.

While evaluating customer loyalty, which is the likelihood of customers continuing to use a service and recommending the same to others, similar features of service quality impact the effect. The attributes of tangibility, reliability, assurance, and empathy are very useful in establishing a good relationship with the clients hence enhancing loyalty. Delivering high quality in the physical characteristics of service delivery, maintaining an unceasing and accurate delivery of services, and staffing adequately informed and courteous personnel are important in the creation of client loyalty. The study's implications the findings are practical in the sense that they provide pharmaceutical importers in Liberia with valuable information. The measures that can help to enhance the service quality are making investments in physical facilities, increasing the dependability of operations, developing staff expertise, emphasizing customer service, and being reactive. The following areas can, therefore help pharmaceutical importers to pay more attention to their clients and gain more satisfaction and loyalty from their clients. All these factors are essential for sustainable competitiveness in the highly saturated pharmaceutical industry.

Service Quality Dimension	Impact on Customer Satisfaction	Impact on Customer Loyalty
Tangibility	Strong positive impact. Modern facilities and neat appearance enhance customer perception of service quality.	High tangibility fosters trust and positive relationships, increasing loyalty
Reliability	Critical for satisfaction. Timely and accurate delivery of pharmaceutical products meets customer expectations.	Consistent reliability builds long-term trust and encourages repeat business and recommendations.
Assurance	Strong positive impact. Competent and courteous staff increase customer confidence in service quality.	Assurance enhances trust and strengthens customer relationships, leading to higher loyalty.
Empathy	Significant positive impact. Personalized consultations and attentive service make customers feel valued	Empathy fosters emotional connections, increasing customer retention and loyalty.
Responsiveness	Moderate positive impact. Quick responses to requests and problems improve customer perceptions of service quality.	Responsiveness enhances customer trust and satisfaction, indirectly supporting loyalty.

Table 4.9: Key Findings

3 Conclusion and recommendation

By dissecting the service quality into five aspects, including tangibility, reliability, assurance, empathy, and responsiveness, the study determined how these aspects influence the customers' perception and behavior. The findings suggest that these factors significantly influence customers' satisfaction and loyalty, which indicates their importance to pharmaceutical importers that aim to enhance their service quality and sustain a competitive edge. Specifically, it revolves around the role of tangibility which is a sub-component of service provision that is physical. Hence, the findings of the study showing the benefits of tangibility in enhancing the level of satisfaction and consumer commitment help in understanding why pharmaceutical importers should invest in good infrastructure and employee attire. Whereas, reliability refers to the capacity of the firm to deliver a standard service that has been offered and has an impact on the level of customer satisfaction and loyalty. Thus, the pharmaceutical sector focuses most on reliability as products need to be delivered on time and correctly. In light of the research evidence derived from the study, it was established that trust and satisfaction are a function of satisfying consumers' expectations of service quality in terms of accuracy and speed hence loyalty.

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made to enhance service delivery and establish long-term customer relationships within Liberia's pharmaceutical import industry.

1. Contemporary infrastructures and equipment should be the initial focus concerning pharmaceutical imports. The appearance of staff members, which includes their attire and name tags, plays a very important role in the creation of a good impression. Introducing modern technology into consumer service, order processing, and inventory control is very beneficial in enhancing the client experience and thereby enhancing their loyalty.
2. Continual training and development activities are very crucial in enhancing the staff members' knowledge and skills, about technical product information and customer service.
3. Supporting those pharmaceutical importers also requires the cooperation of policymakers and regulatory authorities. Vital is a legal act regulating a high level of service quality that has indicators for training of personnel and customer

relations, including rules for staff. These initiatives will be aided even more by utilizing tax advantages when grants are provided for importers who make investments in improving their infrastructure and service quality.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Rashid A, Rokade V. Service quality influence customer satisfaction and loyalty[J].UKH Journal of Social Sciences,2019, 3(1).50-61.
- [2] Quaye-Foli A. An operational marketing plan for Munchies: Improving customer satisfaction and service quality[J].2019.
- [3] Adi PRNC, Basuki R. Effect of brand image and service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty at Bank Jatim Syariah Surabaya[J].Russian Journal of Agricultural and Socio-Economic Sciences,2019, 87(3).152-165.
- [4] Agarwal I, Gowda KR. The effect of airline service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty in India[J].Materials Today: Proceedings,2021, 37.1341-1348.
- [5] Agarwal R, Dhingra S. Factors influencing cloud service quality and their relationship with customer satisfaction and loyalty[J].Heliyon,2023, 9(4).
- [6] Akbar MM, Parvez N. Impact of service quality, trust, and customer satisfaction on customers loyalty[J].ABAC journal,2009, 29(1).
- [7] Supriyanto A, Wiyono BB, Burhanuddin B. Effects of service quality and customer satisfaction on loyalty of bank customers[J].Cogent Business & Management,2021, 8(1).1937847.
- [8] Akroush MN, Dawood SA, Affara IB. Service quality, customer satisfaction and loyalty in the Yemeni mobile service market[J].International Journal of Services, Economics and Management,2015, 7(1).53-73.
- [9] Balinado JR, Prasetyo YT, Young MN, et al. The effect of service quality on customer satisfaction in an automotive after-sales service[J].Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity,2021, 7(2).116.
- [10] Huang P-L, Lee BCY, Chen C-C. The influence of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty in B2B technology service industry[J].Total Quality Management & Business Excellence,2019, 30(13-14).1449-1465.
- [11] Nunkoo R, Teeroovengadam V, Thomas P, Leonard L. Integrating service quality as a second-order factor in a customer satisfaction and loyalty model[J].International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management,2017, 29(12).2978-3005.
- [12] Hafeez S, Muhammad B. The Impact of Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty Programs on Customer's Loyalty: Evidence from Banking Sector of Pakistan[J].International Journal of Business and Social Science,2012, 3(16).
- [13] Gong T, Yi Y. The effect of service quality on customer satisfaction, loyalty, and happiness in five Asian countries[J].Psychology & Marketing,2018, 35(6).427-442.

- [14] Dhisasmitho PP, Kumar S. Understanding customer loyalty in the coffee shop industry (A survey in Jakarta, Indonesia)[J].*British Food Journal*,2020, 122(7).2253-2271.
- [15] Maroco AL, Maroco J. Service quality, customer satisfaction and loyalty[J].*European Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Recreation*,2013, 4(3).118-145.
- [16] Younquoi C, Jalloh A, Onyibe P, Nwosu L. The impact of healthcare service quality dimensions on patient satisfaction: a case study of Ganta United Methodist Hospital, Liberia[J].2023.
- [17] Purnomo DD, Permana AR, Irawan D, Qomariah N. The Influence of Service Quality, Brand Image, and Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty of Bekam Therapy Center Jember[J].*International Journal of Management Science and Information Technology*,2023, 3(2).157-164.
- [18] Wong A, Sohal A. Service quality and customer loyalty perspectives on two levels of retail relationships[J].*Journal of services marketing*,2003, 17(5).495-513.
- [19] Yang KF, Yang HW, Chang WY, Chien HK. The effect of service quality among customer satisfaction, brand loyalty and brand image. In.2017 2017.IEEE.2017.2286-2290.
- [20] Sugiarto S, Octaviana V. Service Quality (SERVQUAL) Dimensions on Customer Satisfaction: Empirical Evidence from Bank Study[J].*Golden Ratio of Marketing and Applied Psychology of Business*,2021, 1(2).93-106.
- [21] Sutrisno A, Andajani E, Widjaja FN. The effects of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty in a logistics company[J].*KnE Social Sciences*,2019.85-92.
- [22] González-Cruz TF, Botella-Carrubi D, Martínez-Fuentes CM. Supervisor leadership style, employee regulatory focus, and leadership performance: A perspectivism approach[J].*Journal of Business Research*,2019, 101.660-667.
- [23] Shrestha PM. Impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty[J].*Management Dynamics*,2021, 24(2).71-80.
- [24] Mahmood A, Rana MLT, Kanwal S. Relationship between Service Quality, Customer Loyalty and Customer Satisfaction[J].*Lahore Journal of Business*,2018, 6(2).
- [25] Balbin-Romero G, Carrera-Mija E, Serrato-Cherres A, Cordova-Buiza F. Relationship between e-banking service quality based on the e-SERVQUAL model and customer satisfaction: a study in a Peruvian bank[J].*Banks and Bank Systems*,2022, 17(4).180.
- [26] Barusman ARP. What Does Service Quality, Perceived Value, and Customer Trust Have to Do with Customer Loyalty for Go-Food Users in The Gojek App? Using Customer Satisfaction Performs as a Moderator.(Case Study on Students of the Faculty of Economics and Business Univ[J].*Kurdish Studies*,2024, 12(2).698-723.
- [27] Chang C-H, Thai VV. Do port security quality and service quality influence customer satisfaction and loyalty?[J].*Maritime Policy & Management*,2016, 43(6).720-736.
- [28] Ali M, Raza SA. Service quality perception and customer satisfaction in Islamic banks of Pakistan: the modified SERVQUAL model[J].*Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*,2017, 28(5-6).559-577.
- [29] Alzoubi H, Alshurideh M, Kurdi B, et al. Does BLE technology contribute towards improving marketing strategies, customers' satisfaction and loyalty? The role of open innovation[J].*International Journal of Data and Network Science*,2022, 6(2).449-460.
- [30] Amiri ASF, Faghani F. Mobile banking service quality and customer satisfaction (application of SERVQUAL model)[J].2012.
- [31] Ariff MSM, Yun LO, Zakuan N, Ismail K. The impacts of service quality and customer satisfaction on customer loyalty in internet banking[J].*Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*,2013, 81.469-473.
- [32] Arora P, Narula S. Linkages between service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty: A literature review[J].*IUP Journal of Marketing Management*,2018, 17(4).30.
- [33] Asadpoor S, Abolfazli A. Effect of electronic service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty Saderat Bank's customers[J].*International Journal of Scientific Study*,2017, 5(4).407-411.
- [34] Ayinaddis SG, Taye BA, Yirsaw BG. Examining the effect of electronic banking service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty: an implication for technological innovation[J].*Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*,2023, 12(1).22.
- [35] Bentum-Micah G, Ma Z, Wang W, et al. Perceived service quality, a key to improved patient satisfaction and loyalty in healthcare delivery: the servqual dimension approach[J].*Journal of Health and Medical Sciences*,2020, 3(2).
- [36] Cano MC, Hijada Ii VM. Canteen service quality and customer satisfaction: a mixed method study[J].*Journal of Tourism, Hospitality & Culinary Arts (JTHCA)*,2024, 16(2).48-80.
- [37] Caruana A. Service loyalty: The effects of service quality and the mediating role of customer satisfaction[J].*European journal of marketing*,2002, 36(7/8).811-828.
- [38] Chingang Nde D, Lukong P. Using the SERVQUAL Model to assess Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction.: An Empirical Study of Grocery Stores in Umeå. In. 2010.
- [39] Chinomona R, Masinge G, Sandada M. The influence of e-service quality on customer perceived value, customer

satisfaction and loyalty in South Africa[J].Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences,2014, 5(9).331-341.

[40] Aghdaie SFA, Faghani F. Mobile banking service quality and customer satisfaction (application of SERVQUAL model)[J].International Journal of Management and Business Research,2012, 2(4).351-361.

[41] Akbar S, Som APM, Wadood F, Alzaidiyeen NJ. Revitalization of service quality to gain customer satisfaction and loyalty[J].International Journal of Business and Management,2010, 5(6).113.

[42] Albarq AN. Applying a SERVQUAL model to measure the impact of service quality on customer loyalty among local Saudi banks in Riyadh[J].American Journal of Industrial and Business Management,2013, 3(08).700.

[43] Chodzaza GE, Gombachika HSH. Service quality, customer satisfaction and loyalty among industrial customers of a public electricity utility in Malawi[J].International Journal of Energy Sector Management,2013, 7(2).269-282.

